

Gaia: the stellar physics challenge of the 21th century

Frédéric Thévenin¹

¹ Université de la Côte d'Azur, Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, CNRS, Nice

Abstract

The Gaia mission is in its fourth year of work and is a key space mission devoted to astrometric measurements of stars. Much more than astrometric data will be delivered in Gaia data release 4 at the end of the nominal mission; the duration of the data acquisition is now foreseen to be extended at least two more years. When the ELTs and PLATO will enter in operation, the full and definitive catalog will be available for many astrophysical goals. Among the long list of subjects is the characterization of exoplanetary systems for which the fundamental parameters of stars, greatly improved by Gaia, is a requirement.

For Gaia data release 2 (April 2018) the most important results have been parallaxes and proper motions of 1.3 billion stars, and 6 million accurate radial velocities. The use of these results deserves some attention and careful reading of the companion papers which explain in details how to use the catalog and their limits. Six months after DR2 many stellar astrophysical new discoveries have already been published on young to very old stars, isolated or in clusters. The return on the physics of stars is already vast and for sure will be a central part of this Cool Star colloquium. The release of 6 million radial velocities is unique and will help stellar astrophysics and galactic structure studies as well. Present or future asteroseismic campaigns with TESS, PLATO, SONG, or studies with the LSST or ELTs combined with Gaia will definitively change our knowledge of the Universe. The revolution is on the way and that is the legacy of an old astrometric tradition for decades. Nonetheless, the future of astrometry has to be foreseen soon after the end of the Gaia mission, the space interferometry is a challenge for that purpose.

1 Introduction

Two billion stars in the Gaia catalog at the end of the mission will represent about 0.5 percent of the stars belonging to the Milky-Way. This objective of the Gaia output catalog will impact results in all parts of astrophysics. Launched 1200 days ago, Gaia (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2016) has started to collect data for science on the 25th July 2014, and the second release of the Gaia catalog was delivered on the 25 April 2018 (Gaia Collaboration et al., 2018). It gives to the scientific community a very impressive view of the potential of the future Gaia catalogs 3 and 4 to reveal the unknown nature of the Milky-Way, unknown stellar physical mechanisms, unknown stellar populations and many more. The impact of the space mission on the astronomical knowledge is so broad that it is impossible to draw an exhaustive list. Considering that the second data release (DR2), done with only 22 months of data collected, has already reached the nominal accuracy expected for some astronomical returns of stellar parameters in the catalog, the end of the mission at least 5 years after the starting date will provide more accurate results than it was estimated with simulated data before the launch.

Gaia has also a social role: it regroups different astrophysical communities, e.g. the planets, the stars, the interstellar medium, the dynamic of the Galaxy, cosmology, galaxy classification, etc. Present Astronomy is under strong domination and influence of large extragalactic surveys and exoplanetary systems studies, both always very impressive which dominate financial budgets and human investments in astrophysics. In that context, it is important to remember that there are many nearby astrophysical and cosmological tools (laboratories) the stars of the Milky-Way: Gaia is demonstrating that stellar physics and stellar population studies are essential. Their use provides important and unique constraints

on our knowledge of the Galactic structure and its evolution (recent or old). These issues relevant to stellar physics improve tools used by extra-galactic community for studying distant stellar populations in external galaxies and the evolution of very distant and post big-bang galaxy formation. It is today more and more recognized that galaxies such as the Milky-Way formed by accretion of small stellar structures, and this Galaxy cannibalism is still continuing today. Massive 3D hydrodynamic simulations of the evolution with time of the Universe show that this scenario of accretion is already on the point to be definitively confirmed by the use of the Gaia survey.

Why Gaia, an astrometric mission, is so important? The main reason is in the distance estimate (stars are candles) and the proper motions for billions of sources, which places it among the most accurate way to get these results in modern geometric work (Thévenin et al., 2017). As an example, the accuracy of the proper motions will be converted at the end of the mission in velocity components with accuracy better than 1 m s^{-1} , then the stellar duplicity down to Jupiter mass planets will be revealed; this is a challenge and a complementary study of the space missions K2, TESS, PLATO. Gaia is the only one astrometric mission done by teams already trained in astrometry with the prototype Hipparcos (ESA). This expertise is unique and it was clear since the beginning of the century the need for a mission that answers many questions that come up today, not only today but in the future with large and deep surveys on sky sources from planets to stars and on cosmology.

A key point today is the coming soon of many accurate large surveys not only in photometry but also in rapid photometry (asteroseismology). The winning combination is Gaia, TESS, PLATO, LSST. A question is already open today:

what will be the future after Gaia? A new Gaia or a more ambitious one toward sub- μ arcsec? It is time to start to think and to carry out a concrete proposal of the future astrometry in Space.

2 Summary of the present status of Gaia and DR2

Currently, there are no major issues with the satellite, all instruments are still at their nominal levels. The degradation of the CCDs of the focal plane is lower than expected which means that a long time extension of the satellite is realistic. If we continue collecting the data during 4 more years, it will represent almost the double of the period of work of the satellite which means more accuracy for astrometry, photometry and radial velocity (RV) outputs. In consequence the number of the published sources could reach 2 billion, and the number of radial velocities could increase to more than 50 million, but more important is the improvement of the RV accuracy at the faint magnitude limit, which is $G=15.5-16$ (at few km s^{-1}). For the astrometry the goal of 7-8 μ arcsec for stars brighter than $G=10$ becomes realistic.

Gaia DR2 is presented in several papers that detailed the catalog and how data have been treated and the results validated: Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018), Arenou et al. (2018), Sartoretti et al. (2018), Lindegren et al. (2018), Evans et al. (2018) for the main ones. Some caveats are well described in companion papers like Arenou et al. (2018). For example, the global astrometry done by Gaia is producing strong correlations which can inhibit a significant improvement in the distance of for example the LMC by using the mean of hundreds of LMC star parallaxes. If one decides to use parallaxes on a group of stars, one should take into account the correlations, which also are important for any transformation of coordinates and proper motions.

Note that when using colours published in DR2, G_{BP} and G_{RP} , one has to look at the *excess of colour* parameter. This is an important caveat, this results from the crowding (overlapping of spectra) and the sky background treatment which both need improvements (more epoch data). This effect can lead to errors in the use of colours see Evans et al. (2018) for astrophysics and is also important for the treatment of the chromaticity in the astrometric solution (leading to systematic errors).

A possibility to select stars for which all the astrometric and photometric treatment is confident is to compute the RUWE parameter as recommended by Lindegren L (UAI, Vienna, 2018). This is just an indicator of quality.

Access to the catalog can be done on two servers: one at ESA (<https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/>) and one at ASI Center (<http://gaiaportal.asdc.asi.it/>).

The distance of stars is always a difficulty because computing the inverse of the parallax can reach important errors as it has been demonstrated with 20 years of the use of the Hipparcos catalog (Luri et al., 2018) in particular when parallaxes are very small compared to uncertainties. Non-DPAC distances using DR2 have been computed using a bayesian approach and are available at the following address: www.mpia.de/~calj/gdr2_distances/main.html and explaining to the user how to use the parallaxes, which depend on the scientific case under study (Bailer-Jones et al., 2018).

3 Gaia a challenge to understand the history of the Milky-Way: on the importance of the stellar Radial Velocity measurements

Stars are not born where they are today, but they are the fossil records of the formation of the Milky-Way which is imprinted in the motions, the chemical composition, and their spatial distribution; stars are also distributed in age. What is not possible to do in distant galaxies we can do in the Milky-Way with the study of stars one by one. If for the brightest stars, transverse motions (Gaia proper motions) can reach accuracy close to 1 m s^{-1} , for faint and very distant stars they remain accurate velocities compared to the third velocity component: the radial velocity (RV). RV is obtained with the spectrometer of Gaia (RVS) (Cropper et al., 2018) which is limited in accuracy to 0.5 km s^{-1} for stars brighter than 12 up to 10 km s^{-1} for faintest ones.

Radial velocities are mandatory to know the velocity vector of the stars, but Gaia is limited in magnitude 14-15 for accurate RVs (few km.s^{-1} of uncertainties), then actual surveys from ground based instruments represent a mandatory effort to extend the RVS sky survey of Gaia in magnitude; a second reason to complete the RVS survey is because Gaia is unable to extract RVs with its integral field spectrograph mode in crowded regions of the Galaxy. At end of the Gaia mission the magnitude 15.5 for the radial velocity catalog is a realistic objective representing more than 50 millions of RVs covering the whole sky. Consequently, ground based spectrographic surveys for RV measurements would have to concentrate more on magnitudes between 15-19 than brighter ones, to help to reconstruct the 6D phase space. Dedicated regions (small parts of the sky because of the limited time telescope available) have to be carefully chosen on the basis of Gaia astrometric studies up to magnitude 19. There are several spectrographic surveys foreseen or already active: APOGEE (Allende Prieto et al., 2008), GALAH (De Silva et al., 2015), GES (Gilmore et al., 2012), LAMOST (Cui et al., 2012), RAVE (Steinmetz et al., 2006), but none are reaching magnitudes 18-19. Then, we encourage strongly TACs of these large spectrographic survey to reconsider the importance of RVs for faint objects compared to chemical detailed analyses which are important to reveal the identity of the stars for galactic studies or for stellar physics tests, but are concerning smaller number of stars because of the need of higher spectrographic resolution at high Signal to Noise Ratio, then with brighter magnitude limits. The ELTs have to foresee to produce such surveys deeper in magnitude in more specific and smaller regions like the Bulge of the Galaxy. Instruments like MOSAIC/ELT could help to complete Gaia RV survey at a fainter end.

Let's remember that a new view of the disk of the Milky-Way is now revealed by the 6 million RVs published in Gaia DR2 (Sartoretti et al., 2018). New structures are appearing or are confirmed like those detailed in several papers like: Gaia Collaboration et al. (2018), Kawata et al. (2018), Antoja et al. (2018). The Galaxy looks now more complex and its large amount of stars are seen not orbiting peacefully around the center. The interaction with our galactic neighbours seems to play an important role (Bland-Hawthorn et al., 2018).

4 Gaia a challenge for fine tuning of the physic of the stars

Wide range of ages and metallicities of large samples of stars belonging to clusters will be a direct probe of different phases of the Milky-Way formation and evolution. But the determination of stellar parameters critically depends on the completeness and accuracy of stellar models. Stellar astrophysics is undergoing significant development due to sophisticated improvements in modelling, but open issues remain, e.g. mixing in the stellar interiors, rotation, binarity and magnetic fields which need both Gaia for the distance and variability characterization but also asteroseismology for accurate constraints on the interiors. Simple parameterisation is often used to treat mechanisms we have not yet completely understood (e.g. the "mixing length" (ML) in treatments of convection). Definitive calibration of the ML parameter with mass, age (evolution), and chemical composition will be done with combined asteroseismic frequencies.

As an example, let consider the star HD122563, giant and metal poor, for which the position in a HR diagram was not reproducible with the ML calibrated on the Sun. Its new distance determination with Gaia and the recent discovery of its asteroseismic oscillation have converged to change a bit the ML from 1.85 to 1.55 for this PopII stars (Creevey et al., A&A submitted 2018) in agreement with 3D simulations (Magic et al., 2015). A careful calibration of that parameter will help to estimate the helium content of stars in globular clusters and halo. Do they fit with the recent big-bang estimate of Y and how Y is evolving with time (e.g. with the metal composition enrichment of the matter in the Milky-Way)? More PopII stars well constrained will definitively figure out the enrichment of helium in the Milky-Way.

Calculations of stellar magnitudes, lifetimes, and burning phase duration are influenced by stellar physics, and need to be calibrated by comparing models and with very accurate observations. This requires precise astrometric, photometric, and spectroscopic data to detect multiplicity and peculiar spectral types as well as various stellar atmospheric disturbances (shells, nebular lines etc), which affect the position of a star in the colour-magnitude diagram (CMD); its interpretation with theoretical Hertzsprung-Russell (HR) diagram could be in error. In the Gaia era, we will have an increasing number of stellar populations where nearly-complete information from the zero-age main sequence to SN explosion will be available. Gaia data, coupled to on-going ground based spectroscopic surveys, will open a new domain of stellar astrophysics for all stellar masses and all evolutionary stages.

It is worth to mention that Gaia can be used to validate the physics already present in the codes to model stars. A beautiful example is done with the CMD for low mass stars done with the Gaia DR2 catalog which has allowed to detect a new gap in the main sequence around the mass $0.35 M_{\odot}$ and that the explanation came out without difficulties and without implementing new physics, see Jao et al. (2018), & MacDonald & Gizis (2018). More accurate position of such anomalies belonging to the main sequence or the giant branch at different metallicities will help to validate both the stellar physics in the codes and consequently the Gaia catalog contents.

5 The binarity: compact companion, small mass companion and exo-planet systems

How many stars are formed with companions? Does binarity depend on the mass and on the initial mass function (IMF) of the cluster where stars formed? Does the metallicity of clusters play a role in the frequency of the binarity, or is it the density of the cluster the main parameter? Once the binary is formed, how often can a star stay in that binary configuration when the primary (most massive one) evolves in a supernova leading to a black hole or a neutron star (compact objects) without ejection from the binary system? All these questions and even more will get some answers with the high accuracy of the astrometric solution in particular such information on faint or invisible companions will be revealed with the study of proper motion anomalies. One of the coordination units of Gaia is working on that important aspect of the stellar formation and evolution history, binarity estimation will be part of Gaia DR3 and DR4. Apart from the faint companion detection, important for statistics, is the extension to the detection of exo-planets: probably a few thousand systems will be discovered by astrometry. A first attempt has been done using the two catalogs Hipparcos (van Leeuwen, 2007) and Gaia DR2 for the closest stars and the statistics look promising (see Kervella et al., submitted A&A 2018). In particular in this study we were able to reproduce the sub-stellar mass distribution until ultra-cool dwarf stars with a bimodality which will have to be understood once confirmed. Then exo-planets are already predictable because the accuracy on proper motions are already at the level of 1 m s^{-1} ! No doubt that Gaia DR3 with multi-epoch proper motions will definitively change our knowledge in that field. Also the masses of binaries will be determined for thousands of systems for which they have been detected and followed at same epochs of Gaia observations in astrometry and with the board RVS spectrograph. It will results in an incredible number of double stars for which all the fundamental parameters will be constrained in particular the ages.

6 Stellar classification completeness

The statistics on the stellar classification as regard to the mass of stars is important for the constraint on Initial Mass Function (IMF) studies in different regions of the Milky-Way. In particular, the knowledge of the mass distribution in the solar environment is teaching us on our past history (Antoja et al. (2018)). With the Gaia DR3 and DR4 catalogs, once the detailed photometry will be available, a complete statistic view of the distribution of stars formed in the Milky-Way in particular in the disk will help to constrain the IMF in different regions and directions; this view depends on the fundamental parameters of about a billion of stars obtained with the Gaia data. For the far past history this is more tricky because it is more and more evident that the Galaxy has formed in an active accretion phase of small structures that have experienced their own IMF and Star Formation Rate (SFR) story.

In the whole Galaxy, determining the upper and lower limits of star mass formation is a challenge and fundamental for that purpose. When stars are too small they miss to initiate thermonuclear reactions and should have to be considered as exo-planets. At what mass is this precise limit? Answering this will help to constrain stellar interior models of such low mass stars: e.g. the equation of state and the opacity,

but also the atmospheres which send information on these objects when they formed and are still hot and cooling. At the opposite end, the largest masses will help in understanding the mass limit of the black holes appearing when they evolve rapidly in supernovae. Beyond this study is also the prediction of the number of supernovae of different types, to predict how many of them can be detected with gravitational waves signature with the current detectors.

A cosmological impact exists in this study not only for the chemical element evolution starting at the beginning of the PopIII stars but also in the study of the ability of the Galaxy to form very massive stars. Our knowledge on stars belonging to the so-called Luminous Blue Variable stars (LBV) have recently changed thanks to Gaia (Smith & Stassun, 2017), most of the BLV are less luminous and then less massive than expected. A better fine tuning of the stellar classification will appear soon.

Among many results already discovered in stellar physics with Gaia, an nice result is the re-estimate of the velocity of stars classified as Hyper Velocity Stars. The number of these discovered stars is revisited (Irrgang et al., 2018).

7 Stellar fundamental parameters: mandatory for any galactic chemical evolution history of the Universe

Masses, radius, chemical composition, effective temperature, ages are the main fundamental parameters of stars. For a given physics, this is enough to compute the right model corresponding to a star placed in a CM/HR diagram. Among the physics in codes of stellar evolution that still need improvement is the stellar rotation and mechanisms of energy and material transport. The high quality of the Gaia mission results will guide us where the model assumptions fail. How efficient is the gravitational settling counterbalanced by extra-mixing for which nothing is none today? Reading carefully the color magnitude diagram (CMD) from Gaia data will help to guide us toward for which stars this is important or not and how much the models fail to reproduce the CM/HR diagram positions and detailed chemical composition. Gaia DR2 has already started to deliver some of the fundamental parameters. There is still a long way before the complete success of this goal but with improvement of the Gaia photometry calibration this will come out (Andrae et al., 2018). An extension of that work with the LSST (Malz et al., 2018) will be a great improvement in the future.

To reach 5% of accuracy on the age of a star requires an accurate distance in the sky. Due to extinction on the line of sight classic methods usually fail. Asteroseismology is an opportunity for that purpose with individual frequencies helping to get a $\log g$ at an accuracy of 0.01 dex. This extreme request on the age of stars is mandatory for the success of the space missions TESS (Ricker et al., 2015) and PLATO (Ragazzo et al., 2016).

The early phase of stars (pre-main sequence) requires accurate distances, which are difficult due to interstellar extinction. The Gaia distance is again very important for these studies. This will help also to draw a 3D map of the interstellar clouds in stellar formation regions.

8 Dynamical CMD to test HR diagram and laws of stellar evolution: activity, variable stars

Stars belonging to some parts of the HR diagram experience variability with short or long periods. They also exhibit activity connected to the magnetic field for which many is already known. The number of data collected in the different class of variable or active stars will reveal at end of the mission a very detailed diagram of these class of stars with statistics connected to the IMF in the different regions of the Galaxy and at different ages. A first and impressive results have been shown on the Gaia potential in that field with the study of M dwarf stars, usually active stars, presenting sequences of evolution that only a large and complete sample offered by Gaia DR2 can reveal (see an example on BY Dra star study Lanzafame et al. (2018)). With the spectra collected by Gaia and its spectrometer the RVS, the S index will be estimated on various stars, not only M type ones, and statistics of the stellar activity among all class of stars will help to better understand the formation of this characteristic and its evolution with time among the populations. Is the physics in the models able to reproduce what will be observed is a challenge?

9 Is the actual Tinsley's concept of the chemical evolution of the Galaxy still valid after Gaia release?

Today it is taught that galaxies form by accretion of gas, producing a generation of stars, which further produce recycling material (pollution) depending on the distribution of the masses of the stars formed (Initial Mass Function). Then this is repeated by a new generation of stars and so on, with new populations occurring more or less frequently (Stellar Formation Rate SFR). This scenario is supposed to exist since the origin of galaxies, and our own in particular. The demonstration by Gaia that the Milky-Way has probably formed in a more complex way with accretion of small structures already formed in distant environment (dwarf spheroidal galaxies for example). They contribute to the halo phase and probably to the disk history, accretion which is still ongoing see Price-Whelan & Bonaca (2018). Then the classic Tinsley's scenario which had good success in reproducing the mean trend in the distribution of alpha elements with respect to Fe, fails to reproduce the double structure or more complex one seen in the disk stars or also in the halo stars that are demonstrated in many work since more than two decades (Nissen & Gustafsson, 2018), Fuhrmann (1998), (Idiart & Thévenin, 2000), (Noguchi, 2018). Higher precision of chemical abundances are expected to be obtained with accurate distances which help to fix the surface gravity of the analysed stars. Therefore, using non-LTE line transfer for the determination of chemical abundances in stars, subtle structures in diagrams of $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ vs $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ will appear more evident, and will have to be understood by considering independent smaller structures accreted. Then Tinsley's model will have to be adapted to conform with this new diagram.

10 Beryllium and Boron stellar abundances in the Galaxy

Currently science and instrumentation concentrate on infrared (IR) spectrographs because of the search for Earth-like exoplanets and extra-terrestrial life signatures in these wavelength ranges. This has pushed the astrophysical community to discontinue developing spectrographs working in the far UV spectral range. The BeII spectral line doublet (303 nm) is observable from ground based telescopes located in high altitudes. For the Boron element, however, its spectral lines at shorter UV wavelengths and only the Hubble space telescope has a UV high resolution spectrograph reaching Boron lines to measure its abundance in the atmospheres of PopII stars. These UV lines are the only one to help to reconstruct the history of the evolution of these light elements which were not formed by the Big-Bang, but produced only in the interstellar medium or stellar environments by spallation nuclear reactions. It is a pity that in the near future we shall not be able to continue to understand the history of the evolution of the Galaxy through these light elements. Once Gaia reveals which stars belong to structures accreted by the Milky-Way to form its Halo a long time ago, it would be very exciting to test how were done the enrichment of these elements with time in these individual structures. Do they follow all the same like what's already understood with few analysed stars that we don't know actually where they were formed: in the halo or in different accreted structures. The actual idea based on the study of these few stars is that the dominant mechanism of the production of these light elements is the cool cosmic ray component taking its origin in the wind (full of C,N,O) of very massive stars producing shocks and breaking on protons of the interstellar medium, and not done with the hot component based on accelerated protons breaking the C,N,O of the interstellar medium (Cassé et al., 2001). We encourage the ELTs community to think about the opportunity to extend spectrographs to UV wavelengths and to the BeII line doublet.

11 Conclusions

A multitude of discoveries are already seen on the horizon after the second release of Gaia. What Gaia DR3, DR4 will be is easy to imagine: a new astronomy is being born done by a huge human collaboration over two decades, a legacy for generations of astronomers.

Acknowledgments

We thank CNES for supporting this work and Orlagh Creevey for critical view of that paper

References

- Allende Prieto, C., Majewski, S. R., Schiavon, R., et al. 2008, *Astronomische Nachrichten*, 329, 1018
- Andrae, R., Fouesneau, M., Creevey, O., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A8
- Antoja, T., Helmi, A., Romero-Gómez, M., et al. 2018, *Nature*, 561, 360
- Arenou, F., Luri, X., Babusiaux, C., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A17
- Bailer-Jones, C. A. L., Rybizki, J., Fouesneau, M., Mantelet, G., & Andrae, R. 2018, *AJ*, 156, 58
- Bland-Hawthorn, J., Sharma, S., Tepper-Garcia, T., et al. 2018, arXiv:1809.02658
- Cassé, M., Vangioni-Flam, E., & Audouze, J. 2001, *Cosmic evolution*, 107
- Cropper, M., Katz, D., Sartoretti, P., et al. 2018, arXiv:1804.09369
- Cui, X.-Q., Zhao, Y.-H., Chu, Y.-Q., et al. 2012, *Research in Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 12, 1197
- De Silva, G. M., Freeman, K. C., Bland-Hawthorn, J., et al. 2015, *MNRAS*, 449, 2604
- Evans, D. W., Riello, M., De Angeli, F., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A4
- Fuhrmann, K. 1998, *A&A*, 338, 161
- Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., et al. 2016, *A&A*, 595, A2
- Gaia Collaboration, Brown, A. G. A., Vallenari, A., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A1
- Gaia Collaboration, Katz, D., Antoja, T., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A11
- Gaia Collaboration, Prusti, T., de Bruijne, J. H. J., et al. 2016, *A&A*, 595, A1
- Gilmore, G., Randich, S., Asplund, M., et al. 2012, *The Messenger*, 147, 25
- Idiart, T., & Thévenin, F. 2000, *ApJ*, 541, 207
- Irrgang, A., Kreuzer, S., & Heber, U. 2018, arXiv:1807.05909
- Jao, W.-C., Henry, T. J., Gies, D. R., & Hambly, N. C. 2018, *ApJL*, 861, L11
- Kawata, D., Baba, J., Ciucă, I., et al. 2018, *MNRAS*, 479, L108
- Lanzafame, A. C., Distefano, E., Messina, S., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A16
- Lindegren, L., Hernández, J., Bombrun, A., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A2
- Luri, X., Brown, A. G. A., Sarro, L. M., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A9
- MacDonald, J., & Gizis, J. 2018, *MNRAS*, 480, 1711
- Magic, Z., Weiss, A., & Asplund, M. 2015, *A&A*, 573, A89
- Malz, A., Hložek, R., Allam, T., Jr, et al. 2018, arXiv:1809.11145
- Nissen, P. E., & Gustafsson, B. 2018, *A&ARv*, 26, 6
- Noguchi, H. 2018, arXiv:1810.00354
- Price-Whelan, A. M., & Bonaca, A. 2018, *ApJL*, 863, L20
- Ragazzoni, R., Magrin, D., Rauer, H., et al. 2016, , 9904, 990428
- Ricker, G. R., Winn, J. N., Vanderspek, R., et al. 2015, *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems*, 1, 014003
- Sartoretti, P., Katz, D., Cropper, M., et al. 2018, *A&A*, 616, A6
- Smith, N., & Stassun, K. G. 2017, *AJ*, 153, 125
- Steinmetz, M., Zwitter, T., Siebert, A., et al. 2006, *AJ*, 132, 1645
- Thévenin, F., Falanga, M., Kuo, C. Y., Pietrzyński, G., & Yamaguchi, M. 2017, *SSRv*, 212, 1787
- van Leeuwen, F. 2007, *A&A*, 474, 653